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How students and companies learned sustainability in mutual Problem Based Learning loops

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ABSTRACT

Problem Based Learning at Aalborg University is centered around projects and group work to enhance the students' learning. In this paper we present two cases where a problem based, real world context was applied in undergraduate environmental management courses at two different campuses, and involving two case companies. The learning of the students and the capacity building at company level were supported as parallel goals. The students learned to handle environmental management at a company level and the companies developed their capacities within these fields. The course started with a visit at the case-company, followed by five lectures where the students did assignments based on the challenges of the case company. At the end, the students presented and discussed their work with the companies. As appropriate case companies, we identified smaller companies who had relevant challenges for the students to work on, and who were interested in environmental management but did not yet have a system. The outcomes of the first two iterations of the course showed that the students got a deep understanding of sustainability issues in theory and in practice, while one company ended up changing their actual practices by e.g. implementing new sustainable business models, and they continued to develop their sustainability efforts after the students' input. In the other company, the collaboration also enhanced learning, but not as successfully due to the type of company and the timing of the interaction between company and students.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Problem Based Learning at Aalborg University (AAU) is part of the tradition of experiential learning, where students learn by applying theory and knowledge to solve problems in complex contexts, also outside academia, and reflect on their experiences [1]. Taking departure in understanding and solving an authentic problem may also lead to enhanced motivation among the students and influence their satisfaction and confidence [2], [3]. At AAU, Problem and Project Based Learning is the foundation for students' learning, and the model encompasses both extensive project work and more subject based courses each semester to support the students' construction of theory and knowledge of relevance for the semester theme. The project work for many students involves cooperation with external partners. Companies and other organizations are also encouraged to contribute with problems or issues, they would like to have students to work on.

As illustrated by Holgaard and Kolmos [4], there are different types of project collaboration between AAU students and companies, from the latter acting as informants, through more case or client based collaboration to shared practices and co-construction of processes and solutions. Their study looked into how the different types of collaboration could inspire the design of educations for employability [4]. This is in line with PBL related research on the impacts of the collaboration, focusing on how working with real problems in a given company can enhance students' learning. Not much PBL research, though, has looked into how the project collaboration may have an impact in the case companies [5]. However, research exists on the impacts of academic research on society, including private companies, and even if they may be differences in perceptions, values, etc., there are mutual benefits from cooperation between academia and the private sector. Not least, in the cases of co-construction of knowledge [5], [6], [7]. Consulting, or client-based projects, in the sense of students solving a given problem for a specific company, is also a recognized learning strategy that may potentially deliver valuable input to the company [3], [8], [9].

Most discussions of academic-practitioner relationships highlight differences in perspectives and intended outcomes, but such relationships may also be considered from a more encompassing standpoint that includes how they may jointly contribute to the creation of common knowledge and understanding on larger social issues like for example climate changes or sustainability [7]. Since PBL based student projects, according to Henriksen et al. [5] have important parallels to academic research practice, it is also relevant to look into the impacts of such projects on a company level.

Phillips [3] argue that the client-based projects may stimulate students' self-directed learning, enable students to learn a specific and practical skill, and facilitate the transfer of skills from the classroom into personal skills for life. However, the lack of structure and instructions that characterizes the self-directed projects may also create frustration and ambiguity among some students. More formalized structure and guidance in the research process could not only reduce the students' negative feelings but also reinforce the positive ones [3].

In an evaluation of a series of client-based projects carried out by students, Grossmann [9] mentions that benefits for the industry depend on the selection of projects, the maturity of students, and the degree of faculty involvement, and range

from stimulus to actionable advice. A small fraction of student projects can even go on to become case studies or applied research. Moreover, industry clients stated that the process of explaining their business and responding to students' questions stimulated valuable new thinking, even if the student deliveries were not of direct use for the company [9]. In a recent, still unpublished, study, Henriksen et al. [5] analysed if and how PBL based student projects with case companies stimulated the creation of mutual values and impact. They distinguished between a potential for impact and a realized impact. The potential impact was affected by the quality of the project including among other things the mutual engagement, coordination, and alignment of expectations, while the realized impact was affected by activities at the company, including what the company invested in the project, how the students' reported their findings and related to the companies, and how, or if, the company decided to continue working with the results [5].

At the AAU bachelor program Urban, Energy and Environmental Planning, sustainability is a major issue for the students to work on. The fifth semester is dedicated to how companies can work systematically to improve their sustainability performance, and students are working with companies during their semester project. Two parallel courses deal with the environmental impacts caused by companies and with the organization of the environmental effort, among other things based on the ISO 14001 Environmental Management Systems standard to familiarize the students with a management system standard approach [10]. The courses are examined on their own, but they also support the students' learning of relevant aspects of potential use in their semester projects. Faculty on one of the courses decided to test if a small scale project together with a case company could facilitate the students' learning of the basics of environmental management in the course, and at the same stimulate the company in advancing its environmental practices. The interaction was also thought to have a positive impact on how the students organized their self-directed semester project.

The purpose of this paper is to reflect on the testing by discussing the following questions:

- What are the outcomes for the students and for the companies of a mutual, PBL based learning loop on how to organize systematic environmental management in the company?
- What to consider when planning and organizing a mutual learning process for students and companies as a part of a course to optimize the learning outcomes?

2 METHODOLOGY

The paper uses a case study approach to analyze how the interaction between students attending a course on environmental management, and selected companies influenced the students' learning outcomes and the companies' environmental practices. The course and the semester projects took place at two campuses in parallel, but were organized and conducted in different ways. This opened for reflections on what may influence the learning outcomes when it comes to planning and implementing, within a PBL framework, the use of small scale projects on course level in combination with larger, student directed semester projects.

Two parallel semesters and courses ran in two different campuses at the university. The analysis took a point of departure in the Aalborg case, since it has run for 2 consecutive years, 2017 and 2018, with the same case company, but with different environmental focus areas determined by the interests of the company. This provided two years of empirical data for the analysis. The Copenhagen case, following the same structure as in Aalborg, but only in 2018, contributed with reflections on lessons learned when working with another type of company and another group of students. The companies were chosen by faculty from these criteria: willingness to cooperate with the students, having relevant environmental challenges for the students to consider, having a physical site for the students to visit not too far from campus.

Case studies often involves numerous sources of evidence [11], and Table 1 presents an overview of the sources of evidence used to evaluate the outcomes of the small scale project in Aalborg.

Table 1. Sources of evidence used for evaluation of outcomes in Aalborg

Source of evidence	Purpose
Learning objectives, curriculum and program of lectures and activities	Understanding the course set-up and purpose
Feedback on steering group meetings	Evaluation of outcomes for the students
Ongoing evaluation on the course and evaluation at the end of the semester	Evaluation of outcomes for the students
Interview with 4 students in 2018 and 4 students in 2019	Evaluating the outcome for students and understanding how motivation is influenced by the “real world” case
Meeting with company before semester start in fall 2018 and fall 2019	Understanding the motivation of the company and preparing the case
Interview with company representatives after the course has ended	Understanding the impacts from the students on the practices etc. of the company

The outcomes for the students in Copenhagen were evaluated from feedback on steering group meetings and from ongoing evaluation during the course and at the end of the semester. Company outcomes were evaluated from oral feedback given by the technical director to the students, by e-mail correspondence between company and faculty after the project, and by statements made by the company in an article published in public media after the project [12].

3 CASES

The following part presents the “Organization of Corporate Environmental Management” course as it was structured in 2017 and 2018 on 5th semester at the bachelor program Urban, Energy and Environmental Planning at Aalborg University. Initially, the course is described from a content perspective. Then follows an analysis of how the course structure resulted in learning outcomes for both the students and the involved case companies (section 4). Finally, there is a discussion (section 5) of success factors for creating mutual learning students and companies, and how this

motivates both students and company, including also aspects that might demotivate students.

3.1 The content of the course

During the course, the students learn how companies over the last approximately 50 years have developed their approach to handling the environmental impacts from production and products, and how this is regulated by the authorities. The first part of the course addresses a systematic approach to environmental management related to both strategic, tactic and practical approaches. The learning objectives focus on understanding how standards for corporate environmental management are implemented in organisations. The students learn, among other things, how to formulate environmental policies and implement these in procedures, goals, targets and action plans in a company. It is in this part of the course, a case company is involved, as illustrated in Table 2:

Table 2. Overview of the small scale project in the course

	Theme/Lecture	Assignment	Interaction with company
Lecture 1	The historic development in corporate environmental management	Different views on corporate environmental management	Site visit and presentation
Lecture 2	Strategic environmental management	Environmental policy	Limited to written information
Lecture 3	Tactic environmental management	Environmental procedures	Limited to written information
Lecture 4	Operational environmental management	Environmental goals and action plan	Limited to written information
Lecture 5	Environmental management – the system	Strategic environmental initiatives	Assignments are presented to the company

During the course, students and companies interacted through a site visit at the first lecture, for students to have a presentation of the company and a real-life experience of the ongoing activities. Written materials of relevance were provided to the students during the following lectures as a part of their working with the requirements in the ISO 14001 standard. At the last lecture, the company visited the university to hear students presenting their analyses and recommendations, followed by a discussion among students, faculty and the company.

The lectures were designed to create a learning loop for both students and companies by having both the site visit in the beginning and the presentation of assignments in the end, where the students needed to reflect on their assignments in order to make a coherent presentation for the company.

As part of the preparation for the oral exam, each student prepared a few slides per lecture as a starting point for explaining the main issues and challenges of implementing environmental management on the different levels, from strategic to

operational, in the case company – including their recommendations to the company. Thus, examination was closely linked to all five steps in the small scale project, and the students had an interest in getting the most out of working with the company case.

3.2 Organization of the interaction with the companies

The preparation of the case is essential for a positive outcome of the case collaboration. It is important to choose a company that faces exactly the kind of challenges that the students’ need to work with to meet the learning objectives of the course. In this case, a company interested in a systematic environmental management system, without having implemented one yet. Also it is important to make it clear to the company that they will not receive “expert solutions and ideas” but need to collaborate with the students to their mutual benefit and learning for both partners. The level of environmental awareness and experiences in the company presents different learning potentials for the students as well as for the companies as shown in Table 3:

Table 3. Overview of learning opportunities

Type of company	Learning opportunities for students	Learning opportunities for company
Proactive environmental management on	Understanding a “best practice” approach. Analysing existing practices and suggest changes	Limited, but may get some new ideas and perspectives on existing practices or potential improvements
Interested in environmental management	Learning how a company operates and suggest how to implement environmental management	Big learning opportunity as they have limited experience but would like to learn
Reactive on environmental management	Learning the importance of (lack of) organisational support. Developing suggestions for how to change priorities and implement a new approach	Potentially the learning opportunities are big but in reality it is hard to implement the ideas

In the Aalborg campus, students worked with a recycling company that were motivated to implement an environmental management system certifiable according to ISO14001. The company had not started implementing a system yet, but the director and the operations manager of the company had both worked in ISO14001 certified organisations before, and had an idea of the potential benefits and obstacles of such a system.

In Copenhagen, students worked with a company leasing equipment to craftsmen and to construction sites. The company had no production of its own, but handled and maintained products from suppliers. The company had a certified Quality, Health & Safety and Environmental Management System, according to DRA (Danish Rental Association), and the company was interested in knowing how they could proceed to a more advanced environmental management as required in the ISO 14001 standard. For practical reasons, the site visit to the company took place only two weeks before the last lecture, not in the beginning.

4 OUTCOMES OF THE MUTUAL LEARNING PROCESS

This section shows the learning outcomes of the students and what the companies

gained through the collaboration.

4.1 Outcomes from a student perspective

Based on feedback from students on semester steering group meetings, through interviews and from the students' reactions after presenting for the case company, the main outcomes, the students gained from cooperating with a specific case company were related to better understanding of real life challenges and opportunities for working systematically with environmental management. Moreover, getting immediate feedback from a potential "customer", the company, helped them understand and assess the relevance and potentials of their ideas and suggestions. This is very important since working with environmental management only from the requirements in a standard may lead to rather hypothetical proposals.

Another positive outcome mentioned was a higher motivation, not the least from realizing that the companies de facto implemented student-based ideas. This was especially important in the second year in Aalborg where examples from the previous year were available. The students in Aalborg also expressed very clearly both years that the fact that they had to present their results to the company, and get their feedback was very motivating. One of the students said:

"All of a sudden we found out that even at the 5. Semester with a new topic at hand, we can actually develop materials that a company finds valuable." (5. Semester student, 2018)

From a teacher and examiner point of view, another type of outcomes also became clear. Presenting analyses and recommendations in a way that made sense for a company, and at the same time being able to bring their learnings and discussions to the academic table during the examination, helped the students bridging practical experiences and academic learning. Moreover, the small scale project with a case company served as a good preparation for the exam, which the students on average passed with high-end grades (*Statistics on grades provided by examiner*).

In Copenhagen, students were also happy to have the chance to work directly with a case company. However, they struggled to find what they thought of as something useful for the company, since the company already did a lot of things. Some students also found the company uninteresting, since it apparently had no major environmental issues to improve. Finally, the rather late site visit meant that the students lacked the on-site experiences when they worked with the strategic and tactical aspects of environmental management.

4.2 Outcomes from a company perspective

The outcomes from the company perspective ranged from ideas and inspiration to specific proposals that could be, and in some cases were, implemented.

In Aalborg 2017, the students focused on how the company could make their business models more proactive in a sustainability context, and they suggested a new model for renting the products to costumers instead of selling them. This secures an increased use of the single product and hence reduced the need to produce more products. A year later, this was implemented as a leading business model for the sale of this product category. In a broader understanding, one can say that the company expands its focus from resource reduction to circular economy as a part of the business model. As another outcome of the collaboration, the company initiated an ongoing collaboration with both Aalborg University and Network for

Business Sustainability in Northern Jutland, to keep focus on strategic environmental management.

In 2018, the students had a focus on how the company managed the machinery and addressed this by suggesting how to involve the employees in the environmental efforts. This led to a change of practices in the company where the employees are now involved in reducing the environmental impacts from production and operation of the company.

Another type of outcome was a discussion of how the products (non-permanent sound reduction walls) could have an added value by using the “back side” of the wall for interaction with the local community in the area. E.g. by being equipped with “climbing walls”.

Thus, the case company in Aalborg was satisfied with the outcomes, as stated by the production manager:

“We find the interaction very enriching. The students come with suggestions that we never considered before, but they do it with respect of who we are” (Manager of the company, 2018).

In Copenhagen, focus for the students was to prepare a new version of the company’s environmental policy, to select a relevant environmental issue (most of them chose waste handling) and to prepare an action plan and procedures that could be incorporated in the existing DRA certified management system. The company did not express any specific areas for the students to look at. Since the intended outcomes was quite open ended for the company, students and faculty prepared a brainstorming list with around 30 suggestions for the company on how to improve their environmental performance. The technical manager responded to the ideas and were especially happy for the suggestions to improve waste handling, to realize market potentials in becoming an ambassador for environmental improvements in the construction sector, and to start co-working with the suppliers, even if it may become challenging. After the project, the company continued working with environmental aspects on a strategic level with a point of departure in the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals. The company contacted the university later to ask if students would like to continue working with them.

“Having 30 people looking into your business is truly a gift. With a larger number of people, we can have many more and new nuances on the way, we run our business” (Quote from the technical manager of the company in the article published on the cooperation) [12]

5 DISCUSSION

For the small scale project to become a successful learning experience for the students, apart from the motivation in itself of providing valuable and useful input to the companies, some aspects are important to consider, even if this case is very small and one should be careful in generalizing. The small scale project took up half the lectures in the course, and one has to be sure that it can cover adequate parts of the learning objectives and provide sufficient understanding for the students on the environmental challenges of companies, both in theory and in practice. Four significant lessons were learned through planning and conducting the small scale projects:

Careful selection of case company. Students attending the course had no previous experiences on companies and how they deal with environmental aspects. They need to establish a basic understanding. As a teacher, it may be tempting to choose companies with best practices to inspire the students. However, the students learned more from challenging themselves to come up with suggestions to the company, than from being informed on what the company was already doing. From a company learning perspective, the optimal situation seemed to be a situation with high interest in environmental management, but not having a system implemented yet.

When constructing the basic understanding of the company's environmental impacts, and how to handle the impacts, students favoured direct impacts that were recognizable when visiting the company. For example, students in Copenhagen found very little direct impacts in their case company, since most of the impacts were indirect and related to either the suppliers/manufacturers of the equipment, or to the phase where the craftsmen used the equipment leased at the case company. The indirect impacts are also relevant in environmental management, but from a learning perspective, they may not be the best way to start.

The mutual learning process co-constructed a common understanding of the formal requirements of the ISO 14001 standard for environmental management, and the challenges a SME faces in implementing a systematic approach as required by the standard. Since small companies struggle with having time to search for background knowledge, the students' digested and adapted knowledge on the standard made it more useful, which may have stimulated the companies to continue working with the issues.

Alignment of expectations on process and outcomes to make sure that the company can and will provide information and constructive feedback to the students. This means that the company in advance has agreed to spend time and resources on providing data and information for the students, but also that the students will share their documents with the companies afterwards. As for the outcomes, students need information on what expected deliveries are, since they may be afraid of making a fool of themselves in front of the company.

Timing of meetings between students and company to support that mutual learning can take place. It is important that the students visit the company early in the process, as this creates the foundation for working with assignments related to the case. In addition, an early visit creates an opportunity for the company to influence the relevance of the work made by the students.

Structure of the project. A clear and determined structure of the small scale project is needed to secure the fulfilment of learning objectives. Relating each lecture with a requirement for the exam proved to be effective in having all students' focus on active participation, even if they may not be very interested in the topic of environmental management on the mandatory course. Moreover, the clear structure in the small scale project served as a stepping stone for the students to transfer the learnings into their self-organized semester projects that were started up in parallel to the course, but with a longer time frame. This may help overcome the ambiguity and frustrations, some students face especially in the beginning of the self-directed projects.

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